

Method for Collective Work in a Two-Dimensional Dynamic Network

Description and Moderator's Guide

Abstract. This guide describes the method we developed for conflict-free collective work of large groups within a two-dimensional dynamic network (using the example of 15–35 participants interacting in a peer-to-peer format). The method is the result of integrating task decomposition, brainstorming, and the cross-group method into a unified whole to enable the development, discussion, harmonization, and adoption of collective decisions. The guide contains detailed instructions for moderators and participants, a step-by-step algorithm, and a sample personal protocol. After several cycles of use, the method allows participants to work independently – without a moderator. It can be applied in political, civic, and business organizations to address a wide range of complex issues and tasks.

Keywords: collective work, two-dimensional dynamic network, large groups, cross-groups, sectoral groups.

The method for collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network¹ is designed to organize the development, discussion, harmonization, and adoption of decisions within large groups ranging from 9 to 100 participants interacting in a peer-to-peer format.

The method for collective activity in a dynamic network includes the method for collective work in a two-dimensional or three-dimensional² dynamic network, integrated with classical project management practices. It is intended for organizing the development, discussion, harmonization, adoption, approval, and implementation of decisions within large groups ranging from several dozen to one thousand participants, within political, civic, and business organizations.

The theoretical and technological foundations of the functioning of different-level party subdivisions according to the method for collective activity in a dynamic network are presented in the book³.

¹ Plakhtiy, T. (May 30, 2014). The Procedure of Group Work in Two- and Three-Dimensional Dynamic Networks. *SSRN*. Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2544458>

² Plakhtiy, T. (June 15, 2010). Three-Dimensional Dynamic Network and Its Practical Application in Socio-Political Activity. *Zgroup*. Available at:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20160402052449/http://zgroup.com.ua/article.php?articleid=4016> [in Ukrainian]

³ Plakhtiy, Taras. (2025). Political Parties of the Next Generation: Theoretical and Technological Principles of Their Activity, Procedure for Their Establishment and Deployment. 2nd ed., rev. and enl. Lviv: Magnolia 2006.

This document provides a description and a moderator's guide for collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network involving large groups of 15 to 35 participants. It is intended primarily to demonstrate the capabilities and potential of the developed method to group leaders and participants. It should also be noted that the three-dimensional dynamic network enables simultaneous conflict-free collective work involving up to one thousand participants.

A visualization of collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network can be viewed here⁴. The work of a large group in a three-dimensional dynamic network can be viewed here⁵. Photos and links to videos from 170 events conducted using the method for collective work in a dynamic network are available here⁶.

Interaction in a peer-to-peer format is maintained by preventing interpersonal and intergroup conflicts through organizational and technological tools, all of which constitute the method for collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network and are described below in Section 2.

1. Preparation for conducting collective work of participants of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network

To prepare for conducting collective work of participants of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network, the following parameters should be discussed and determined with the group's leaders or coordinators:

- **The number of participants** who will take part in the discussion (for demonstration purposes, 15 to 35 individuals is optimal);
- **The number and content of questions** for the small sectoral groups (the ideal number of participants in a sectoral group is 4 to 7; for a large group of 15 to 35 participants, the number of questions can range from 3 to 9, with 3 to 5 being optimal);
- **The time frame for the large group's work** in the dynamic network (the recommended duration is approximately 3 hours, depending on the number of participants and the number of questions);
- **The suitability of the venue for the large group's work** (the space should be large enough and equipped with movable tables and a sufficient number of chairs. The number of tables must be no less than the number of sectoral groups or the number of participants in them – whichever is greater).

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⁴ Plakhtiy, T. (November 12, 2014 [May 11, 2011]). Self-governing dynamic network as an effective alternative to the hierarchical construction. Video Presentation. *T. Plakhtiy – YouTube Channel*. Available at: <https://youtu.be/AyN5vrtelw>

⁵ Plakhtiy, T. (May 1, 2014). Three-Dimensional Dynamic Network at the Forum of Public Initiatives 29.04.2014. *T. Plakhtiy – YouTube Channel*. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=seXNARm-8Y8> [in Ukrainian]

⁶ Plakhtiy, T. (June 16, 2021). TEN YEARS WITH A DYNAMIC NETWORK: Photo-/Video-Story 2010 – 2020. *Dynamic Networks: Theory and Technology*. Available at: <https://tarasplakhtiy.files.wordpress.com/2021/06/fotoistoriadm-2010-2020.pdf> [in Ukrainian]

Once these parameters are set, personal paper-based protocols for participants should be prepared using the template provided in Table 1 below.

The file containing the layout of the protocols is available here⁷. After downloading the file, the title of the relevant sectoral issue must be entered into each protocol for the corresponding sectoral group.

The cross-group numbers should be entered manually – in sequential order starting from 1 – using a **red** pen on each printed A4-format personal protocol.

The number of cross-groups must match the maximum number of participants in any single sectoral group. The total number of printed protocols must be equal to or greater than the number of participants in the large group.

Table numbers must also be prepared. Their quantity should match either the number of sectoral groups or the number of participants in them – whichever is greater. Table numbers can be produced using standard A4 sheets by downloading and printing the layout file⁸.

If possible, participants should be pre-assigned to sectoral groups – either randomly or according to a selected criterion, such as their expertise related to the respective sectoral topic.

2. Step-by-step description of the method for collective work of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network

The algorithm of the method for conducting collective work of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network is presented in Scheme 1.

It integrates the following organizational and technological tools into a single process: task decomposition, brainstorming, and the method of cross-groups.

2.1. Step 1 – “Problem formulation”

At the first step of the method for collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network, a plenary session is held, during which the agenda is presented and a specific issue (task) is assigned to each sectoral group into which the participants are divided.

⁷ Templates of personal paper-based protocols for participants of collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network. Dynamic Networks: Theory and Technology. May 24, 2025. URL: https://tarasplakhtiy.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/templates_dm.docx

⁸ Templates of table numbers based on A4-format sheets. Dynamic Networks: Theory and Technology. May 24, 2025. URL: https://tarasplakhtiy.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/maket_no_stoliv.pdf

Scheme 1. Algorithm of the method for collective work of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network.

If there was no prior distribution of participants into sectoral groups, the moderator announces the method of distribution, which is implemented at the beginning of the next step, when participants take their seats at the numbered tables of the sectoral groups.

At this step, the escalation of interpersonal and intergroup conflicts is prevented by excluding any discussion of alternative versions of the agenda and any discussion of approaches to distributing participants of the large group into sectoral groups.

The content of the sectoral tasks, following the welcoming remarks, is presented either by the leaders or coordinators of the large group or directly by the moderator of the collective work in the dynamic network.

The moderator's final phrase at the end of this step is: "I kindly ask all participants to proceed to the tables of the sectoral groups and take the seats already arranged (according to the prior distribution or by selecting a table based on your preferences regarding the sectoral issue)."

During the distribution of participants into sectoral groups, the moderator monitors the orderliness of their movement to the tables, ensures a balanced distribution across the groups, and addresses the causes of any potential conflicts. In addition, if the large group includes already-formed and cohesive subgroups, the moderator ensures that members of such subgroups are seated at different tables, rather than gathering at the same sectoral group table.

2.2. Step 2 – “Development”

At the second step of the method for collective work of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network, the first stage of brainstorming is conducted within all sectoral groups. During this stage, participants generate lists of components or alternatives for solving their assigned sectoral issues or agenda tasks – without any discussion.

These lists, developed in this way, are recorded by the participants of the sectoral groups in the corresponding columns of the pre-prepared personal paper-based protocols on A4-format sheets.

The escalation of interpersonal conflicts at this stage is prevented by the rules of brainstorming, which prohibit any criticism of the components or alternative draft decisions proposed by other participants.

The escalation of intergroup conflicts, which may arise in the following steps as a result of different sectoral groups developing alternative draft decisions to the same task, is prevented through the decomposition of the general problem – that is, by formulating and assigning a unique issue or task to each sectoral group as a part of the overall problem.

The moderator’s introductory phrase at the beginning of the step: “We are starting the work in sectoral groups in brainstorming mode. Brainstorming involves generating ideas for solving the sectoral issue or task and recording them in the personal paper-based protocols by all participants of each sectoral group. The duration of the session is 50 minutes⁹. By the end of this session, each participant of a sectoral group must have an **identical** list of components or alternative draft decisions for the sectoral issue or task recorded in his or her personal protocol. Each participant will present this list to his or her cross-group in the next step.”

During the collective work of participants in the sectoral groups, the moderator monitors their compliance with the main rule of brainstorming – not to criticize the components or alternative draft decisions proposed by others regarding the sectoral issue or task.

The moderator’s final phrase at the end of the step: “Please proceed to the cross-groups at the tables whose numbers correspond to the number marked in **red** on your personal working protocols.”

2.3. Step 3 – “Discussion”

At the third step of the method, participants are restructured into cross-groups, and the components or alternative draft decisions developed by the sectoral groups for each sectoral issue or task are discussed, with the results recorded in the corresponding columns of the personal paper-based protocols.

This step simultaneously constitutes the second stage of brainstorming and the first stage of the method of cross-groups.

⁹ The optimal duration is indicated here and below; the moderator may adjust it for each specific case.

Thus, in practice, at the third step, each participant in a cross-group takes turns presenting the results of the work of his or her former sectoral group, which completed its task in the previous step and was then disbanded. The other participants in the cross-group (representatives of other sectoral groups) provide additions, comments, objections, or suggestions. The presenter records all of these in the appropriate column of his or her personal paper-based working protocol.

The escalation of interpersonal conflicts at this stage is prevented by the decomposition of tasks, as a result of which each presenter introduces alternative draft decisions for a unique issue or task assigned to his or her sectoral group. This eliminates direct competition between the presenters.

Additionally, such escalation is prevented by organizing the work of the large group's participants according to the method of cross-groups, within which all individuals interact not as autonomous personalities, but as representatives of their previous – sectoral – groups. This structure also makes it impossible to provoke aggression in the presenter (and, consequently, to escalate the conflict) in response to criticism of his or her report, as the report is perceived as the product of the previous – sectoral – group's work. The presenter does not take the critique personally, but regards it as directed toward his or her sectoral group and calmly records it in the personal paper-based protocol, intending to share it with that group at the next step of the method.

It should be noted that in this case, the act of recording itself serves as a **channel factor**¹⁰ that encourages participants to cooperate – that is, it systemically determines their behavioral response to criticism: they simply write its content in their personal protocol.

At the same time, the work of participants in cross-groups breaks down the group boundaries of the sectoral groups, which – if not disrupted – tend to grow stronger, and the groups themselves become encapsulated – that is, more closed, cohesive, and aggressive in competitive interaction with other such groups.

The moderator's introductory phrase at the beginning of the step: “We are starting the work in cross-groups. Each participant of a cross-group will take turns presenting the results of the work of his or her previous – sectoral – group, while the other members of the cross-group provide additions, comments, objections, or suggestions. The presenter records all of these in the corresponding column of his or her personal paper-based protocol. Each participant is allocated 12–15 minutes. The total working time of each cross-group is 60 minutes.”

During the collective work of participants in the cross-groups, the moderator monitors adherence to the allotted time frames for each participant. If any participant exceeds the given time limit, the moderator must stop the discussion of his or her report in the respective cross-group and give the floor to the next participant.

The moderator's final phrase at the end of the step: “Please return to the tables where you worked during the previous step.”

¹⁰ Ross, L., Nisbett, R. (1999). The person and the situation: Perspectives of social psychology. Moscow: Aspekt Press [in Russian]

2.4. Step 4 – “Harmonization”

At the fourth step of the method for collective work of a large group in a two-dimensional dynamic network, participants return to their previous – sectoral – groups, where they report the additions, comments, objections, and suggestions received in the cross-groups. They then form and harmonize a collective group position regarding these inputs, develop a final harmonized draft, and in some cases, alternative drafts for solving the sectoral issue or task. At the same time, they record all the results of their work at this step in the corresponding columns of their personal paper-based protocols.

In addition, at the fourth step of the method, participants of each sectoral group select a presenter from among themselves who will subsequently present the final draft or drafts of the decision at the next step – during the plenary session – for the purpose of adopting one of them through voting.

The escalation of interpersonal conflicts at this step, as at the previous one, is prevented by organizing the work of the large group’s participants according to the method of cross-groups, within which all individuals interact not as autonomous personalities but as representatives of previous groups. This prevents any possibility of provoking aggression in the presenter in response to criticism of his or her report with additions, comments, objections, and suggestions – as this report is the product of collective work in his or her previous, in this case – cross-group.

The moderator’s introductory phrase at the beginning of the step: “We are starting the work in sectoral groups. Each participant briefly presents the additions, comments, objections, and suggestions received in the cross-groups. He or she has 5–7 minutes for this. Together, the participants of each sectoral group form and harmonize a collective position regarding what they have heard, and develop and harmonize a final draft – and in some cases, alternative drafts – for solving the sectoral issue or task. At the same time, they record all the results of their work at this step in the corresponding columns of their personal paper-based protocols. Each sectoral group selects a presenter from among its participants who will then present the final draft or drafts of the decision at the next step – the plenary session of the large group. The total duration of this step is 40 minutes.”

During the collective work of participants in the sectoral groups at the fourth step, the moderator monitors the readiness of each group and whether a presenter has been selected to present its draft or drafts of the decision at the plenary session.

The moderator’s final phrase at the end of the step: “Please transition to the plenary session format by turning to face the area from which the representatives of the sectoral groups will be presenting.”

2.5. Step 5 – “Adoption”

At the fifth step, all participants gather for the plenary session, during which the main or alternative decision drafts for each sectoral issue or task are presented one by one by the sectoral group representatives.

Each presented draft is followed by a general vote by a show of hands. If the voting result is positive, the draft is granted the status of a decision adopted by the large group.

The escalation of interpersonal conflicts at this step is prevented by the absence of any opportunity to discuss the presented decision drafts, as they have already been discussed during the previous steps of the method.

Participants of the plenary session may only ask for clarification regarding the reasons why their suggestions, additions, or comments were not taken into account in the draft decisions of other sectoral groups – **in order to determine their position on these drafts during the voting process.**

The moderator’s introductory phrase at the beginning of the step: “We are beginning the plenary session. The representative of each sectoral group will have 3–5 minutes to present the developed draft or drafts of the decision regarding the issue or task of his or her sectoral group. After each presentation, other participants of the plenary session may ask for clarification (without discussion) as to why their comments, criticism, suggestions, or objections were rejected, in order to determine their position on these drafts during the vote. This will be followed by voting on the presented draft, the result of which will determine whether it is adopted or rejected. The total duration of this step is up to 30 minutes.”

During the collective work of participants at the plenary session, the moderator monitors the time limits for each presentation, gives the floor to other participants for questions, filters out any questions related to the content of the presentations, puts the presented drafts to a vote, and announces the voting results.

The moderator’s final phrase at the end of the step: “I kindly ask all presenters from the sectoral groups to prepare digital versions of the decision drafts they presented for their sectoral issues or tasks and send them to the leaders or coordinators of the large group for further distribution to all participants of today’s meeting. Thank you all for participating in the collective work!”

3. General recommendations

At the beginning of the collective work of large group participants in a two-dimensional dynamic network, the moderator should emphasize the distinction between its implementation as part of a training session and in a real organization.

If it is a training session, voting on the draft decisions presented at the plenary session by the sectoral groups is not mandatory. Moreover, each such group may present two or more alternative draft decisions regarding its sectoral issue.

The outcome of collective work in a dynamic network involving participants of a large group of employees, members, and invited experts within a real organization is the set of draft decisions from the sectoral groups adopted through voting. In such cases, these decisions should be understood as those draft decisions that the large group supports, is ready to implement, and takes responsibility for – including any potential consequences of implementation.

At the same time, the moderator should encourage participants of each sectoral group to develop and agree upon a single draft decision. However, if this proves impossible and more than one alternative draft decision is submitted by a sectoral group, the moderator must explain to the large group the differences between possible next steps in the context of a training session and those in a real organization.

That is, the moderator should emphasize that under no circumstances can any decision be considered final or absolute. If flaws or errors become apparent later – or if negative consequences arise during implementation – such decisions may and should be revised at a similar meeting within a real organization.

Obviously, in the case of a training session, no further interaction among the large group participants is expected, which makes it impossible for them to continue working collectively with the adopted draft decisions.

If certain participants of the large group possess strong charisma and are unwilling to abandon their own draft decisions – even when their flaws or shortcomings are obvious to the rest of the participants – they should still be given the opportunity to present these drafts, with a clear emphasis that this is allowed only within the framework of a training session. In the context of a real organization, the large group must select and adopt, through voting, a single decision from among all the alternative draft decisions presented.

At the same time, the moderator must emphasize that there are no decisions that are one hundred percent true or correct. Each decision is only conditionally valid or correct at a particular moment in time for a specific large group that supported the draft developed and presented by one of its integral parts – a small, specialized sectoral group.

Within the framework of a training session, if necessary, the large group may conduct a vote on alternative draft decisions during its plenary session at the final stage of the process – after these drafts have been presented by the representative(s) of the corresponding sectoral group. Obviously, in this case, such voting merely reflects the attitude of the large group toward each draft decision; it does not determine their validity or correctness, and it certainly does not ensure their implementation.

In contrast, during the collective work of a large group of employees, members, and invited experts of a real organization within a dynamic network, the adoption of a single, agreed-upon decision from each sectoral group is a necessary condition for its subsequent implementation.

Returning to the practical aspects of implementing the method of collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network, it should be noted that under real conditions, the number of participants in the sectoral groups within the large group may vary. Ideally, the difference should not exceed one or two individuals.

In such a case, either one cross-group operates with an incomplete composition – meaning that its participants do not discuss one of the lists of components or alternatives – or several cross-groups include two representatives from the same sectoral group, who coordinate with each other to decide who will present the results of his or her group's work. In the first scenario, within the allotted time, it is advisable to invite a participant from another cross-group – one who has already presented the results of his or her sectoral group – to present on behalf of the sectoral group not represented in the cross-group.

A distinctive feature of the presented method of collective work in a two-dimensional dynamic network is that, after completing the third cycle of work within the same large group, its participants will be able to continue working

independently, without a moderator, using a regular timer to set the time intervals for group work at different steps of the method.

4. Personal paper-based protocols of participants in collective work within a two-dimensional dynamic network

Table 1 presents the simplest version of the personal paper-based protocol used by each participant in the collective work within a two-dimensional dynamic network.

Table 1. Sample of the most basic personal paper-based protocol of a participant in a two-dimensional dynamic network.

1 Sectoral group	Formulation of the sectoral issue or task from the agenda	3 Cross-group
Step 2. Work in the sectoral group		Step 3. Work in the cross-group
List of alternatives for solving the issue on the sectoral agenda		Additions, comments, objections, and suggestions concerning the list of alternatives
Step 4. Work in the sectoral group	Final draft of the sectoral group's decision	

For addressing simple issues or tasks, the protocol can be printed in A4 format. For more complex and comprehensive problems, it is advisable to increase its size to A3 format.

At the top of the personal protocol, the title of the issue assigned to the respective sectoral group should be indicated. On the left, the number of the sectoral group should be noted, and on the right – the number of the cross-group, highlighted in red. This highlighting facilitates and simplifies the transition to cross-groups for implementing the third step of the method.

The protocol is divided into three sections to accommodate entries for the second, third, and fourth steps of the collective work method in the dynamic network.

Each participant fills out all columns of the protocol personally. As noted above, this functions, on the one hand, as a channel factor, encouraging participants to collaborate with colleagues, and on the other hand – it prevents manipulation of the final decision's content.

This same channel factor ensures that each participant can potentially act as a presenter on behalf of his or her sectoral group and ensures written documentation of the large group's results under any circumstances.

The results recorded by each sectoral group can be digitized after their adoption and immediately distributed to all participants.

It is important to note that, after completing the second step, each participant must have an identical list of components or alternative draft decisions recorded in the first column of the protocol. These are the items the participant will present in his or her cross-group during the third step of the collective work in the dynamic network.

At the third step, in the second column of the protocol, each participant must personally record the additions, comments, suggestions, and objections to his or her report received in the cross-group. The participant will then personally present these in the initial sectoral group during the fourth step of the method.

After the fourth step, the third column of each participant's protocol must contain the final draft decision of the sectoral group, which one of them will present at the plenary session for voting.

Once participants have become familiar with the method of collective work described here, the same format may be used as a shared virtual protocol of the sectoral group in the cloud.

In the context of developing, discussing, harmonizing, adopting, and approving decisions during strategic sessions, we recommend modifying and extending the protocol format to suit each stage of such a session¹¹. These protocol forms continue to evolve and may vary in appearance depending on the specific requirements of the event.

The written documentation of results at every step ensures automatic oversight by all members of a sectoral group regarding the authenticity of the final draft decision presented at the plenary session by their designated presenter. The importance of such oversight has been repeatedly confirmed in our practice¹².

¹¹ Plakhtiy, T. (March 10, 2017). Strategic Planning in a Dynamic Network: A Methodological Guide. *Dynamic Networks. Theory and Technology*. Available at: <https://tarasplakhtiy.wordpress.com/2017/03/10/3807/> [in Ukrainian]

¹² Plakhtiy, T. (June 16, 2021). TEN YEARS WITH A DYNAMIC NETWORK: Photo-/Video-Story 2010 – 2020. *Dynamic Networks: Theory and Technology*. Available at: <https://tarasplakhtiy.files.wordpress.com/2021/06/fotoistoriadm-2010-2020.pdf> [in Ukrainian]